

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF POLYARYLSULFONE TOUGHENED EPOXY SYSTEMS

D. Ding, K.K. Cheng
Composites Research Lab
Feng-Chia University
Taiwan R.O.C. 40724

ABSTRACT

Fracture toughness of polyarylsulfone modified epoxy systems and their composites is characterized by the critical strain energy release rate, G_c . The G_{Ic} of neat resins is measured from compact tension specimen (CTS), while the interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} of the composites are obtained from the double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notched flexure (ENF) specimen, respectively. The resulting resin systems show several times improvement in the G_{Ic} value, and still maintain good mechanical properties and heat resistant property. Their composites also show significant improvement in the interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic} & G_{IIc}). A good correlation of fracture toughness between neat resins and their composites are found. With brittle matrix (resin G_{Ic} less than 320 J/m^2), the composite interlaminar fracture toughness (G_{Ic} & G_{IIc}) is greater than the resin; For tough matrix (resin G_{Ic} higher than 320 J/m^2), an increase of 3 J/m^2 in resin results in approximately a 1 J/m^2 increase for the composite. This less than complete transfer of toughness from resin to composite is attributed to the fibers restricting the crack-tip deformation zone. Scanning electron microscopy pictures of DCB fracture surface in composites are characterized by river markings, while the hackle markings dominate ENF fracture surface. Both of these are different from neat resins fracture surface.

KEYWORDS: Fracture toughness; neat resin / composites; polyarylsulfone toughened epoxy; fractography

1. INTRODUCTION

The early study of toughening brittle epoxy matrix with liquid rubber have success in the improvement in fracture toughness but impaired hot-wet mechanical strength. Toughening thermosetting epoxy without deteriorating the glass transition temperature T_g is by the route of addition a thermoplastic polymer. The requirement for these polymers are amorphous, high T_g and good mechanical properties. These polymers are either compatible with the epoxy, forming a homogeneous Semi-IPN structure [polyaromatic thermoplastic (1); polyethersulfone (PES), ICI Victrex 3600 (2)], or incompatible with the epoxy, forming a two phase system [polyetherimide (3,4), polyethersulfone, ICI Victrex 100^P (5,6) 300^P (7,8)]. High doping of polymer might even cause a phase inversion, while the continuous phase in the thermoplastic polymer [polyethersulfone, Union carbide Udel 1700 (9)]. Here a new thormoplastic polymer- polyarylsulfone (PAR) have been blended with the epoxy system. The improvemsent of fracture toughness in neat resin and its transfer to composite's interlaminar fracture toughness is addressed in this communications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials The basic bifunctional epoxy resin diglycidyl ether bisphenol A (DGEBA) from Shell (EPON 826) was cured with 30 phr hardening agent 4-4'-diaminodiphenyl sulfone (DDS) from Anchor (ANCAMINE SP) . The epoxy system is modified by different phr of polyarylsulfone (PAR), which was obtained from Amoco Performance Products (Radel 100).

The PAR chips is first micronized to the powder form. Various amount of PAR powder is dissolved in epoxy at 180 °C, after cooling to 130 °C hardening agent DDS is added, mixtures is degassed and poured into the mold. The same curing cycle is used for the unmodified and PAR modified systems: at 130 °C for 1 hr., rise to 160 °C for 2 hr., finally at 190 °C for 2.5 hr. The cooling down shall be slow to avoid the occurrence of crack.

The unidirectional carbon fiber prepreg of the modified epoxy system is done on a drum winding machine in our laboratory, while methylene chloride is used as the solvent to control the viscosity. The cure cycle for the composites is a two stage scheme with dwelling at 110 °C for 1.5 hr, and keeping at 190 °C for 2.5 hr in an autoclave.

2.2 Testing Methods The tensile test is done in accordance with ASTM D638 on a MTS machine at a crosshead speed of 5mm/min. T_g measurements by either DSC or DMA are studied by a Dupond 9900 system at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. The mode I fracture toughness is done on the compact tension specimen (CTS) at a crosshead speed of 5mm/min in compliance with the ASTM E-399 procedure.

The fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) and fracture energy (G_{Ic}) are related by the following relationship.

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{K_{Ic}^2}{E} (1-\nu^2)$$

where tensile initial modulus is used for E. Poisson's ratio ν is assumed equal to 0.35 for all materials used. The interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} of the composite is done on the double cantilever beam (DCB) for mode I, at loading rate 5mm/min ; while in the sliding mode II, G_{IIc} , end notched flexure (ENF) is used on a Zwick machine at a crosshead speed of 5mm/min.

The morphological observation on the fracture surface of CTS, DCB and ENF samples is done on a SEM (model Canada Nanolab 2100).

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Tensile strength, tensile initial modulus and T_g of various blends along with the unmodified system are summarized in table 1.

TABLE 1

The properties of epoxy systems with different concentration of PAR

Concentration of PAR (phr)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	tensile initial modulus (GPa)	glass transition temperature (°C)	
			DMA	DSC
0	69.3	2.81	193	187
5	71.5	2.75	186	183
10	73.9	2.69	186	183
15	70.1	2.61	183	181
20	67.6	2.58	183	180

The tensile strength and tensile initial modulus results show little variation in the PAR modified epoxy material in comparison with the unmodified system. The glass transition temperature measured by DMA show a monotonic decrease from 193 °C for a pure system to 183 °C for a 20 phr PAR modified system. The corresponding DSC measurement on T_g shows a smaller drop (from 187 °C to 180 °C). So the PAR modified epoxy system still hold the tensile & thermal properties.

From the dynamic mechanical spectra (data not shown), the PAR modified system, in contrast to the phase separated system (5,7), show a sharp $\tan \delta$ $T \alpha$ transition. The $T \beta$ transition of $\tan \delta$ shift to higher temperature as the concentration of PAR increased. The SEM fractography Fig.1 and Fig.2 of the PAR modified CTS sample and methylene chloride etched surface don't give any evidence of phase separation. We are tentatively assigned this is a homogeneous Semi-IPN system.

Fig.1 SEM fractography of blend containing 20 phr PAR

Fig.2 SEM fractography of blend containing 20 phr PAR, etched in methylene chloride

Fracture toughness K_{Ic} and fracture energy G_{Ic} as a function of the amount of PAR added are shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4. The data is the mean values of at least six specimens where the amount of scattering is within 2%.

Fig.3 Fracture toughness (K_{Ic}) of epoxy systems with different concentrations of PAR

Fig.4 Fracture energy (G_{Ic}) of epoxy systems with different concentrations of PAR

Both K_{Ic} and G_{Ic} results show a monotonic increase as the amount of PAR is increased. At 20 phr PAR added, K_{Ic} value shows a 100% improvement and the G_{Ic} value gives a 340% gain. Previous result on 20 phr PES/DGEBA/DDS system give a G_{Ic} value of 1.02 kJm^{-2} , which is comparable with the present value of 1.1 kJm^{-2} (2).

The interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite at 10 and 20 phr PAR modified system are shown in Table 2 for the mode I and mode II,

Table 2 Interlaminar Fracture toughness of resins and composites

PAR concentration (wt%)	Resin	Compositte *	
	G_{Ic} (J/m ²)	G_{Ic} (J/m ²)	G_{IIc} (J/m ²)
control	250	291	459
10	550	465	646
20	1100	624	802

*Vf = 60 ± 3%

along with the unmodified system for comparison, The G_{Ic} values for neat resin are also listed for reference. If we follow Hunston (10), the interlaminar fracture toughness is plotted against the fracture energy of neat resin in Fig.5, the initial slope of the curve are slightly larger than 1.0, which might come from the fiber bridging. As in the latter part, the transfer of neat resin fracture energy to interlaminar fracture toughness is 30% which is compatible with the 34% reported value from Hunston's (10), These results can be explained by the Yee's (11) constraining effect. The presence of stiff fiber decrease the size of the plastic zone in the interlaminar layer in comparison with the size of uncontrained bulk polymer.

Fig.5 Relationship between interlaminar G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} of composite and G_{Ic} of neat resin. $\square G_{Ic}$ $+ G_{IIc}$

The SEM fractography of DCB (mode I) of the unidirectional composite are shown in Fig 6. and 7. for unmodified and modified system, respectively.

The PAR modified system show more extent of river markings and branched crack sstructure than the unmodified system.

Fig.6 Postmortem fractography of Mode I DCB specimen

Fig.7 Postmortem fractography of Mode I DCB specimen for 10 and 20 phr PAR/EPOXY composite

Fig.8 Postmortem fractography of Mode II ENF specimen

Fig.9 Postmortem fractography of Mode II ENF specimen for 10 and 20 phr PAR/EPOXY composite

The SEM fractography of ENF are shown in Fig. 8 and 9 for unmodified and modified system, respectively. The distinguished hackle markings for mode II are presented. The larger plastic deformations both in mode I and II fractograph, can explain the toughening effect of PAR modified epoxy system.

4. REFERENCE

1. M.S. Sefton, P.T. McGrail; J.A. Peacock; S.P. Wilkinson; R.A. Crick; M.Davies; G.Almen 19th International SAMPE Technical Conference, 700-710 (1987)
2. C.H. Chen and D. Ding Proc. of the 1989 Annual Conf. of The Chinese Soc. for Mat. Sci. 551-554
3. C.B. Bucknall and A.H. Gilbert Polymer, 30, 213-217 (1989)
4. C.L. Chung; H.P. Lin; D. Ding, Proc. of the 1991 Annual Conf. of the Chinese Soc. for Mat. Sci. Apr.26-27
5. C.B. Bucknall and I. K. Partridge. Polymer 24, 639-644 (1983)
6. C.B. Bucknall and I. K. Partridge. British Polymer J. 15, 71-75 (1983)
7. R.S. Raghava J. Poly Sci Part B 25, 1017-1031 (1987)
8. R.S. Raghava J. Poly Sci Part B 26, 65-81 (1988)
9. G.R. Almen, P.Mackenzie, V. Malhotra, R.K. Maskell, P.T. McGrail. M. S. Sefton 20th International SAMPE Technical Conference, 46-59 (1988)
10. D.L. Hunston. ASTM Composites Technology Review. 6, 176 (1984)

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the National Science Council (NSC 79-0405-E035-10).

